

URSULA RABAR

**OAEBUDT
Community
Consultation
Results January
2023 - July 2023**

Acknowledgment

This work was made possible by the Mellon Foundation through the [Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks](#) Grant, and by the 73 participants that contributed in anonymous online and in-person activities facilitated via Mentimeter during workshops, active sessions and presentations at conferences. Christina Drummond and Ursula Rabar designed and facilitated the processes that generated the input for this document. Ursula Rabar prepared this report.

Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the community consultations facilitated by the Open Access Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) team (Executive Director, Christina Drummond, and Community Manager, Ursula Rabar) from January to July 2023. Feedback was sought on issues related to open access book usage (OAEBU) data exchange within an international data space (IDS). The information received was analysed and documented herein to inform the [Advancing to Launch](#) project team as well as the task team developing the IDS Rulebook.

Table of Contents

01

Community
Consultations
Overview

02

Results

03

Conclusion

Community Consultations Overview

Strategy

The goal of the OAEBUDT community consultations has always been to engage with the community of relevant stakeholders, gather their input and feedback as well as ensure its work is well-informed on aspects that might be missing while developing the effort. Similar types of consultations have been done through the Data Trust's previous grants as well (example: Neylon, Cameron. (2021). OA eBook Usage (OAeBU) Metadata Community Consultation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6422062>). With that in mind, the answers to the January to July community consultations have been analysed in order to portray common points across the stakeholder groups to understand how they work with OAEBU data and what concerns they have and what is needed to ensure trust in the OAEBU data exchange via an IDS model.

Methods

From January until the end of July 2023, the OAEBUDT team facilitated four community feedback sessions at different conferences either online or in person:

Date	Conference	Stakeholder type	Type of presentation	Title of the presentation
8th -11th May 2023	Library Publishing Forum (LPCForum)	Libraries, library publishers, university presses	Active session	Book usage metric sharing and use guardrails
31st May - 2nd June 2023	Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP)	Library publishers, society publishers, service/technology providers	Panel discussion	Unpacking OA Usage Reporting - What Do Stakeholders Want?
12th - 15th June 2023	Open Repositories (OR2023)	Repositories, library publishers, university presses, commercial publishers	Panel discussion	Supporting Trusted OA Usage Data Reporting and Analytics through Shared Infrastructure
11th - 13th July 2023	International Conference on Performance Measurements in Libraries (LibPMC)	Libraries, library publishers, university presses	Panel discussion	Book usage metric sharing and use guardrails

Table 1. List of conferences and events for the community consultation Jan-Jul 2023

Event participation allowed different stakeholders to provide feedback on draft ethical principles, community governance structures, and data trust participation requirements prepared by stakeholders for community review. The attendees explored the importance of book usage data stewardship practices and policies, and why high-quality, granular open access (OA) book usage analytics and reports may require detailed usage data to be exchanged in controlled environments as opposed to aggregate data harvested from the public web. Issues of privacy, transparency, community governance, and security were explored while considering whether specific use and reuse limitations should exist for book usage data shared across the book publishing ecosystem.

The tools used during those events were PowerPoint presentations to relay the necessary information and Mentimeter audience polls to create engagement and discussion. The polls were answered live during the sessions. Two types of questions were used: open questions and voting on provided options. In addition, participants were invited to sign up for future focus groups at the end of each session.

The table below presents the Mentimeter questions used during the community consultations, the number of poll participants at each event, and the number of responses gathered per each question (poll participants were allowed to submit multiple answers to the same question):

Mentimeter question	Conference	Number of participants in the poll	Number of responses
How do you work with OA book usage data?	LPCForum, LibPMC	53	37
What benefits do you see in having better access to OA book usage data?	LPCForum	23	23
What would you add regarding data quality?	LPCForum	23	9
What would you add as an OA Usage Data Provider?	LPCForum, LibPMC, SSP	71	37
What would you add as an OA Usage Data Consumer?	LPCForum, SSP, OR2023	43	23
What would help you trust that the people and organizations participating in data exchange are held accountable to community rules?	LPCForum	23	5
What concerns or solutions do you have on ensuring usage data exchange and processing will not harm readers or authors?	SSP	18	8
What else do you require to have trust and transparency in OA usage and impact reporting and analytics?	SSP	18	4

Table 2. Mentimeter questions for community consultation Jan-Jul 2023

Altogether, across 73 poll participants, 146 responses were collected, and distributed as per the below graph:

Image 1. Mentimeter poll answers distribution per event

A full overview of the dataset is available on this link: <https://zenodo.org/record/8304127>.

Parallel to the community consultations listed in this document, there was a different approach used for poster presentations. Given the limited time, the focus when engaging stakeholders at poster presentations was on sharing the past as well as current activities of the OAEBUDT and the below action points:

- sing up for future focus groups,
- fill in a Qualtrics survey with Rulebook development questions in line with the 21-22 April 2023 OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Use Guidelines and Principles workshop (<https://zenodo.org/record/8319929>),
- where to find more information,
- how to stay in touch.

This contributed to the overall number of focus group sign-ups (11 since January 2023) across 2 stakeholder types: libraries and university presses (the other actions the OAEBUDT team took to share the signup form were to make it available via the OAEBUDT website, https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfrCZULFiPezpQi3KIGG9zhBDQnLWmjAO4Ok1NmUnU4eqd6tA/view_form, and to use it during in-person or online conversations in addition to the here mentioned community consultations).

Results

Topic 1: The Value of Open Access Book Usage Data

As per the 2022 report OA eBook Usage Data Analytics and Reporting Use-cases by Stakeholder (Drummond, Christina, & Hawkins, Kevin. (2022). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5889141>), the OAEBUDT works with the premise that book publishers, publishing platforms and services, and libraries all rely on OAEBU data to inform their operations. Across these industries, staff must address the burden of managing and curating usage data provisioned in COUNTER-compliant and non-compliant reports. In order to establish a data exchange that would address these issues, it is important to understand the audience, the way they look at usage data and if there are any aspects the OAEBUDT needs to particularly take into consideration. With that purpose, during the LPCForum active session, we gathered the below 23 responses provided by 17 participants on the question: 'What benefits do they see in having better access to OAEBU data?'

What benefits do you see in having better access to OA book usage data?

23 Responses

Easier to ask for coll-dev money reallocation to OA.	More timely access to data	Make better tenure-and-promotion arguments about impact
Help faculty who are up for tenure talk about their impact	We need usage data to understand future direction. Creating a better data structure allows me to publish OA books on multiple discovery platforms.	Authors being able to demonstrate the reach of their work more easily (eg for tenure and promotion cases)
To better promote oa to authors	Encouraging scholars to publish OA by being able to point to it's ability to further reach/impact	A better understanding of how are books are being received out in the world, and how we might improve
Multiple platform usage	We could provide more frequent information to authors on the use of their books	Tenure and promotion considerations
Easier to argue against anti-OA scholarly societies (eg. AHA)	We could use the data to advocate for more support for OA	Potential for a single place to exchange usage data. Simplifies workflows (hopefully).
Potential for better measures of quality of use and impact of books	To justify further institutional support for OA	Provides more ways to work with faculty
Include this book usage data as part of an OER grant program at my institution (impact for scholars)	Need analytics to provide to collection development committee	Comparable data to paid and subscription data
Demo impact for educational use of Oa	Help inform university community about impact and guide decisions	

Image 2. Answers to the question 'What benefits do you see in having better access to OA book usage data?' at LPCForum 2023.

Secondly, to understand more context behind the data usage practices, we asked the question ‘How do you work with OAEBU data?’ at LPC Forum in terms of 3 options: if they generate usage data, if they use it for internal or external purposes. This same question was posed at LibPMC as an open question to gather more diversity in data and see what other context it would gather (if any).

Image 3. Answers to the question ‘How do you work with OA book usage data?’ at LPC Forum 2023

How do you work with OA book usage data?
22 Responses

I use this data as a publisher to populate an OA dashboard we maintain internally.	We don't currently but that's because of the laborious effort of collating it	Not very much yet, just as a component of COUNTER reports
We'd like to use it to analyse the impact of OA book data	We don't look at OA book usage - library perspective	We don't do much, focusing upon paid content - have added to the "to do" list :-)
Not at this time.	It is indeed challenging to aggregate OA usage data, especially as we receive it through different systems from our restricted access data.	OA book usage data is helpful for showing the value of OA to faculty & administrators at my university
Yes, as a publisher trying to create our own OA dashboard, it is A LOT of work. And we really don't have the capacity to manage all the sources. Especially when new ones come on board all the time.	We don't prioritize collecting data for titles we don't directly pay for.	I do not work with this data
we dont		
Don't currently	We don't	We use Counter data for OA usage, but this obviously only accounts for usage when users have logged in somehow, we only collect it once a year
I do not work with this data myself. Not sure what my colleagues collect/work with	downloads to show faculty research impact would be useful	We haven't typically because we weren't confident of the reliability of it.
As we support more S2O type book models we need to show more ROI as a library.	We don't look at it yet b/c of the difficulty of collecting it, although the OAPEN Books Analytics Dashboard is starting to address this	We don't

Image 4. Answers to the question ‘How do you work with OA book usage data?’ at LibPMC 2023

Based on these answers, it surfaced that many of the stakeholders use OAEBU data in a balanced way for internal and external purposes while some only generate it. Additionally, the LibPMC open question showed that some don't use OAEBU data due to the time and resources staff needs to dedicate to the aggregation and curation of such data, the reliability of the data, the fact that it isn't a priority and similar. Some of the answers shared that the stakeholders would like to use it more for the purpose of analyzing the impact of OA books or showing the value of OA to administration and faculty. All of these confirm the results of the before-mentioned 2022 report.

Topic 2: Points Raised by the Potential OAEBU Data Providers and Data Recipients

The issues explored for participating in the data exchange during the community consultation addressed two perspectives, the one of data providers as well as the one of data recipients (a role that is referenced as “data consumers” by the broader global International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model - <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-G/tree/main/Glossary>). It was important to gather feedback on what could represent blockers for participation in the Data Trust, whether an entity provides and/or receives data.

Data Providers - responses

What would you add as an OA Usage Data Provider?

5 Responses

Data minimization principles and processes -- data that doesn't exist can't be hacked or leaked.

Unacceptable practices include but are not limited to: precise end-user geolocation, precise timestamps, user (re)identification, behavioral tracking, IP address storage

Sharing/selling data with data brokers (beyond the data that is already open) is an unacceptable practice.

These principles are all very good! Appreciate them! Careful documentation of what the data do/don't mean and their limitations would help with usage-metric misuse.

Align with DORA insofar possible? (Declaration on Research Assessment)

Image 5. Answers to the question ‘What would you add as an OA Usage Data Provider?’ at LPCForum 2023

As a data provider what are your concerns and potential solutions for participating in an OA Book Usage data space?

6 Responses

I would echo the concerns re: privacy. I would perhaps address it by asking users to (voluntarily) share what they are accessing the content for (Eg. business, personal, academic etc)

As a data provider, I would be a bit concerned about my platform's performance being judged against other platforms' performance.

I am not a data provider. But privacy, security are concerns.

Yes, we already have an opt-in way of users sharing their stories. This would complement the quantitative data we would hope to get from the data trust.

I am not sure what I should be concerned about exactly, but the use that AI tool providers are making of data sets (and open content) is an area of concern.

As a smaller data provider with many other burdens, I'd want to make the feeding of data easy.

Image 6. Answers to the question ‘As a data provider what are your concerns and potential solutions for participating in an OA Book Usage Data space?’ at LibPMC 2023

What concerns or solutions would you add as a potential usage data provider?

25 Responses

Potentially seen as antitrust activity	Community input and oversight	Security of data
Making sure no PID is shared where it shouldn't be	Privacy	Competitive advantage given away
Privacy	Publicly displaying low usage	Accuracy
Uptake of usage measurement	Data sources	Accuracy - comparing apples to apples
Scholarship around this usage data being used to drive research agendas	Standards for aggregation and interop	Transparency
Proper licence tagging	The importance of context and privacy for authors	Differences across platforms
Data interpretation	Trust in the slicing and dicing of the recorded usage	Use of data out of context in a way that misleads or does a disservice to authors or disciplines.
Data manipulation	Frequency of updates and availability	Is the data skewed by undetected bots? Are the numbers true?
Use around book banning in specific territories		

Image 7. Answers to the question 'What concerns or solutions would you add as a potential usage data provider?' at SSP 2023

Potential Data Providers reflected on the questions and a few common points emerged:

- Privacy concerns related to personal data
- Accuracy of the usage data exchanged
- Misuse of the usage data exchanged
- Security of the data (be it usage or personal data)
- Alignment with other initiatives

What concerns or solutions would you add as a potential usage data consumer?

13 Responses

Image 8. Answers to the question ‘What would you add as an OA Usage Data Consumer?’ at SSP 2023

What would you add?

4 Responses

Image 9. Answers to the question ‘What would you add (as data consumer)?’ at LPCForum 2023

Potential Data Recipients reflected on the questions and a few common points emerged:

- Authenticity of the exchanged data
- Misuse of the usage data exchanged
- Clarity on the type of data exchanged
- Privacy concerns related to personal data
- Alignment with other initiatives

Data Quality

Additionally, the question on data quality has been posed at LPCForum to explore what else emerges if the question is presented to the poll participants differently.

What would you add regarding data quality?

9 Responses

Image 10. Answers to the question 'What would you add regarding data quality' at LPCForum 2023

Summary

Overall it transpired that the poll participants had similar concerns across all the stakeholder types present. These apply to both types of potential OAEBUDT participants (Providers and Recipients) and also align with the conclusions of the Brussels April 2023 workshop (an in-person working session for 22 diverse OA book stakeholders that generated a first draft of OA book usage data sharing and reuse requirements and principles - <https://zenodo.org/record/8319929>).

Topic 3: Trust

The concept of trust within an IDS is crucial and lays the foundation for data exchange. There needs to be trust in the data, in the processes and in other participants. Therefore it was essential to ask the poll participants what they see as necessary to have within an OAEBU data exchange to establish trust.

What would help you trust that the people and organizations participating in data exchange are held accountable to community rules?

5 Responses

Image 11. Answers to the question 'What would help you trust that the people and organizations participating in data exchange are held accountable to community rules?' at LPCForum 2023.

Trust in OA Usage Data You Receive as an OA User Data Consumer

6 Responses

Open	Community driven	Community governance
Sustainable	Network of usage metrics for normalization	Transparent about data processing steps

Trust in participating as an OA Usage Data Provider

1 Response

Solutions - do we need the equivalent of "robots.txt" for repositories and repository associated information to restrict access to harvesters (eg IIm model builders)

Image 12. Answers to the questions about Trust needed in the data exchange as Data Providers and Consumers at OR 2023

What else do you require to have trust and transparency in OA usage and impact reporting and analytics?

4 Responses

Transparency on the data source - proof of how it's being collected	Request is easy and accessible	I want to know it's not being sold to be used in a way that might not align with our values.
It should not be used as a sign of quality of research		

What concerns or solutions do you have on ensuring usage data exchange and processing will not harm readers or authors ?

8 Responses

Anonymity	Aggregation interpretation	More quantitative "measures of success" that incentivize wrong focus in research
Platform security	Will this affect what is published or rejected	Beware of crowd editing and review
Well intended use of data	Walking the fine line between the granularity required for meaningful interpretation and the anonymity for privacy will be crucial.	

Image 13. Answers to the questions about Trust needed in the data exchange as Data Providers and Consumers at SSP 2023

Summary

The main takeaway message based on all the answers provided by the poll participants was that trust is built by addressing privacy, data misuse and transparency. They confirmed that proper certification, platform and data security are key to establishing and maintaining trust.

Conclusion

The feedback gathered by the OAEBUDT team from January to July 2023 has been very valuable for the validation of the current [Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks](#) Grant work related to OAEBUD exchange within an IDS. Such activities will be part of the project moving forward to gather feedback within the rest of the Work Packages where necessary and appropriate.

Would you like to get involved?

Sign up for our focus groups and announcement list here:
<https://bit.ly/3q00nkh>.